

METHODS OF CONDUCTING MARKETING RESEARCH IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the collection, analysis and interpretation of data by observing what people do and say, observations and inferences, qualitative nature, conducting various surveys based on the use of structured closed-type questions, which are answered by a large number of respondents.*

Key words: *research, market, analysis, survey, structure, need, situation, product, competition.*

Introduction. On Saturation of the consumer market with goods and services is one of the most important areas of improving the well-being of the population. It not only contributes to a more complete satisfaction of needs, but also helps to improve the culture of consumption, develop competition and, on this basis, increase the rate of socio-economic development of society. In this regard, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan pays great attention to the state of the consumer market and the increase in the production of goods and services.

The most important direction of solving the problem of sustainable and rational saturation of the market with goods and services is to ensure the release of domestic goods in a volume and assortment that fully covers the solvent demand of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan. To do this, domestic enterprises must be focused on the production of final products that are truly in demand on the consumer market. To achieve this, in our opinion, it is necessary to fulfill the following conditions:

Firstly: have complete information about the structure of demand for a given product and the dynamics of its change;

Secondly: to form a system for the effective use of this information in the activities of manufacturing enterprises.

In turn, this direction requires the development of methods for research and forecasting demand and the development of new organizational principles for the production of consumer goods. It should be noted that in recent years, many studies have been conducted devoted to solving the above-mentioned problems of improving market relations. At the same time, the current difficulties in satisfying consumer demand show the insufficient development of existing marketing research methods.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In the economic literature, there are many different views on the essence and concept of efficiency, as well as its various criteria and indicators are classified. Many authors emphasize that efficiency is a relative indicator and recommend that it be determined by the ratio of costs to the obtained (achieved) result.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing in the economy, while the researches conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years stemmed from national characteristics. These

include M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov. Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkho'jaev, B. Khodiev, K.Mirzayev, SH. Ergashkhodjaeva, SH. Musaeva and others can be included.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. As noted above, the decision on the need to conduct marketing research depends on the existing marketing information system. It is the lack of information that pushes firms to organize independent research. Conducting independent marketing research requires studying the features and limits of the application of various methods of market research and the collection of unsystematic information. Marketing research uses a variety of different research methods, which can be combined into the following groups: a) document analysis methods; b) qualitative research methods; c) quantitative research methods.

Fig. 3. Classification features of marketing research methods

Since the objectives of the study include conducting independent marketing research, we decided to dwell in more detail on the nature and limits of using the most common research methods. Document analysis methods are used mainly when there is a sufficient amount of

secondary and primary data, the collection of which is carried out in the course of other types of activities.

Qualitative research involves collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data by observing what people do and say. The observations and conclusions are qualitative and non-standardized. Qualitative data can be converted into quantitative form, but this is preceded by special procedures.

Quantitative research is usually identified with conducting various surveys based on the use of structured closed-type questions answered by a large number of respondents. The characteristic features of such research are: a clearly defined format of the data collected and the sources of its receipt. The processing of the collected data is carried out using ordered procedures, mainly quantitative in nature.

Competent translation of primary and especially secondary data into target information requires knowledge of methods of analyzing the data being studied. The entire set of carriers of such data, primarily printed ones, are usually called documents, although the interpretation of information carriers varies in different literature. We also join the opinion of most authors and will call these data documents. Document analysis can be traditional and formalized.

Traditional analysis is a chain of mental, logical constructions aimed at identifying the essence of the analyzed material from a certain point of view that interests the researcher in each specific case. In traditional analysis, external and internal analysis are distinguished.

External analysis is an analysis of the document context in the true sense of the word and all the circumstances that accompanied its appearance. The purpose of external analysis is to establish the type of document, its form, time and place of appearance, who was its author and initiator, what goals were pursued when creating it, how reliable and trustworthy it is, etc. Internal analysis is a study of the essence of the document. All the work of the marketer is aimed at, in this case, conducting an internal analysis of the document, including identifying the level of reliability of the facts and figures provided, establishing the level of competence of the author of the document, clarifying his personal attitude to the facts described in the document. The variety of document types, purposes of their compilation, styles and formats leads to the fact that each researcher tries to see confirmation of his own hypothesis in the document.

The desire to get rid of the subjectivity of traditional analysis gave rise to the development of fundamentally different, formalized (quantitative) methods of analysis or content analysis.

Content analysis is a technique for drawing conclusions based on the objective and systematic identification of text characteristics that are relevant to the research objectives. It is assumed that the application of such a technique includes certain standardized procedures, often involving measurement, so that the data obtained must have the level of generalization specified in the study.

The main areas of use of content analysis are:

- a) identification and assessment of text characteristics as indicators of certain aspects of the object being studied;
- b) clarification of the reasons that generated the messages;
- c) assessment of the impact of the message;

The uniqueness of qualitative methods of marketing research has led to the emergence of several directions of their development, for example, observation, focus groups, in-depth interviews, protocol analysis, projection, physiological measurements.

Qualitative research is based on observational methods that involve passively monitoring the respondent's behavior, usually without explaining the reasons for such behavior.

Observation in marketing research is a method of collecting primary marketing information about the object being studied by observing selected groups of people, actions and situations. In this case, the researcher directly perceives and records all factors related to the object being studied and significant from the point of view of the objectives of the study.

The variety of observation methods is determined by four approaches to their implementation: direct or indirect observation, open or hidden, structured or unstructured, carried out with the help of humans or mechanical means.

Direct observation involves directly observing the behavior of, say, shoppers in a store. Indirect observation involves studying the results of a particular behavior rather than the behavior itself. Archival data are often used here. Physical evidence of certain events may also be studied.

Overt observation assumes that people know that they are being observed, for example, when conducting special experiments. However, the presence of observers influences the behavior of those being observed, so it is necessary to strive to reduce it to a minimum. Covert observation satisfies these requirements, when the subject does not assume that he is being observed.

When conducting structured observation, the observer determines in advance what he will observe and record. All other types of conduct are ignored. A standard observation sheet is often used, which reduces the observer's time expenditure to a minimum. An example of this is the action of tax authorities at the operation of cash registers, when students observed the procedure for registering transactions in trade.

Structured observation is used to verify the results obtained by other methods, to clarify them. It can also be used as the main method of collecting information to accurately describe the object of the study and to test certain hypotheses.

When unstructured observation is conducted, the observer records all types of behavior in the episode being studied. This type of behavior is often used in exploratory research. For example, a company that produces construction tools might send its employees to study the directions and frequency of use of the tool in building houses. The results of the observations are used to improve the tool.

The focus group method is a study of behavior, way of thinking and the nature of the factors in action on a small group of people, whose activities are directed by an instructor-luderator. The group focuses on discussing individual problems and finding new ways to solve them. The main thing in this method is to identify the features of the formation of needs in different categories of consumers.

There are five main purposes for using the focus group method:

1. Generating ideas, such as relative directions for improving existing products, their design, packaging, or developing new products.
2. Studying the colloquial vocabulary of consumers, which can be useful, say, when running an advertising campaign, compiling questionnaires, etc.
3. Familiarization with consumer demands, their perceptions, motives and their attitudes towards the product being studied, its brand, and its promotion methods, which is very important when determining the goals of marketing research.
4. Better understanding of data collected through quantitative research.
5. Study of emotional and behavioral reactions to certain types of advertising.

Directed qualitative methods include in-depth interviews.

A depth interview is a series of probing questions asked by a trained interviewer to a respondent in order to understand why group members behave in a certain way or what they think about a certain issue. The respondent is asked questions on the topic under study, to which he answers in a free form. This method is used to collect information on new concepts, design, advertising and other methods of product promotion; it helps to better understand consumer behavior, the emotional and personal aspects of consumers' lives, decision-making at an individual level, and to obtain data on the use of certain products.

Protocol analysis involves placing the respondent in a specific decision-making situation, where he or she must verbally describe all the factors and arguments that guided the decision-making process. Sometimes a tape recorder is used when using this method. The protocol analysis method is used when analyzing decisions that are distributed over time. In addition, this method is used when analyzing decisions that are very short in their adoption process.

Projection methods place respondents in certain simulated situations in the hope that respondents will reveal information about themselves that cannot be obtained through direct questioning. The following specific methods can be identified as part of projection methods: associative methods, sentence completion tests, picture testing, role playing, and retrospective interviews.

Associative methods include associative conversations and associative word testing or word associations.

Qualitative methods also include physiological measurements based on the study of involuntary reactions of respondents to marketing stimuli using special equipment. For example, the dilation and movement of pupils is studied when examining certain products, etc. Further, the study of eclectic activity and sweating of the skin of respondents is conducted, however, this technique is unusual in nature, so it can cause nervousness in respondents. In addition, its use does not allow separating positive reactions from negative ones.

Finally, the third group of marketing research methods, or quantitative methods, is a tool for obtaining data from statistical or mathematical procedures. First of all, these include survey methods.

A survey involves collecting primary information by directly asking people questions about their level of knowledge, attitudes towards the product, preferences and purchasing behavior; the survey can be structured or unstructured.

The survey methods have the following advantages:

1. A high level of standardization, due to the fact that all respondents are asked the same questions with the same answer options.
2. The ease of implementation lies in the fact that it is not necessary to visit respondents by sending them questionnaires by mail or telephone; there is no need to use technical means and involve highly qualified professionals.
3. The ability to conduct a deep analysis lies in asking successive clarifying questions.
4. The possibility of tabulation and statistical analysis lies in the use of methods of mathematical statistics and corresponding application software packages for personal computers.
5. The ability to analyze the results obtained in relation to specific market segments is due to the ability to subdivide the overall sample into separate half-samples in accordance with demographic and other criteria.

A type of survey method is a panel survey. The basic concept of the panel survey method is the concept of a panel.

A panel is a sample of surveyed units that are subject to repeated research, with the subject of the research remaining constant. Panel members may be individual consumers, families, trade organizations, experts, who, with certain reservations, remain constant. The panel survey method has advantages over conventional one-time surveys: it makes it possible to compare the results of subsequent surveys with the results of previous ones and to establish trends and patterns in the development of the phenomena being studied; it ensures a higher representativeness of the sample in relation to the general population.

The following results can be obtained during panel surveys:

- factors influencing the object of study and their dynamics, opinions and assessments of respondents regarding goods and trade organizations, their change over time,
- reasons decisions and intentions of respondents and their implementation, differences in the behavior of consumers belonging to different social classes, living in different regions, cities and settlements of different types, motives for purchase and predict their development.

While a survey requires a narrow range of responses to a question, quantitative methods such as interviews provide more detailed information about consumers.

The following methods of data collection can be distinguished when conducting surveys with the participation of interviewers or when respondents fill out questionnaires themselves:

1. Interview conducted at the respondent's home. It is possible to agree on the time of the telephone interview in advance. This method usually makes it easier to establish trusting relationships, and it is possible to show samples of the product, advertising materials, etc. However, this is an expensive method of data collection.

2. Interviewing visitors to large stores. Companies conducting such surveys may have offices in large stores. Store visitors are interviewed by an interviewer in the store or are invited to give an interview in the office.

3. Interviews in offices. Usually used to collect information about industrial, technical and office products.

4. Traditional telephone interview. The advantages of this method include: The advantages of data collection include the following: relatively low cost, the ability to cover a large number of respondents and ensure a high level of representativeness, and the ability to be carried out in a relatively short period of time.

5. A telephone interview from a specially equipped room, in which several interviewers work in parallel, and controllers can connect to their telephones.

6. Group independent completion of questionnaires. This approach is used for convenience and to reduce the cost of interviewing.

7. Self-completion of questionnaires left behind. This is a survey option based on self-completion of questionnaires. After a preliminary oral explanation of the goals and objectives of the survey, the questionnaire is left with the respondent. The completed questionnaire is taken from the respondent or he sends it by mail in an envelope with a paid response.

All of the above groups of methods have their own advantages and disadvantages, which is why it is necessary to take an individual approach to choosing a marketing research method in each specific case.

When conducting my own research in the process of writing my master's thesis, I used most

of the above methods of marketing research. At the same time, to develop and conduct further marketing research at Samarkand-Apparel LLC, we compared the above groups of marketing research methods by several features. As the data in the table show, each group of methods has advantages and disadvantages that should be taken into account when defining the problem and developing a research plan.

Table 1

Brief description of marketing research methods

Sign	Document Analysis Methods	Qualitative methods	Quantitative methods
Type of information received	Secondary	Primary	Primary
Specific costs	Low	Tall	Moderate
Reliability of information	Tall	Average	Tall
Form of information received	Standard	Arbitrary	Statistical
The main advantage of the methods	Accessibility and simplicity	Variety and high precision	Breadth of coverage and generalizability
The main disadvantage	Insufficient precision	High cost	Multi-stage

In conclusion, thus, theoretical studies of the marketing management process allow us to conclude that all decisions are based on information about market factors, the main source of which is marketing research. In addition, marketing research is the bearer of the philosophy of the marketing approach to the organization of the production activities of the enterprise, which determines their role in marketing activities.

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